

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Annex 4.5 to AD4.1 – Hair Sampling Questionnaire for Children (6 – 11 years)

WP 4

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¹ PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other program participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history

Version	Date	Reviewer name/Institutions	Short description of changes
Version 1	2023-06-22	Liese Gilles /VITO/ liese.gilles@vito.be; Marta Esteban López /ISCIII/ m.esteban@isciii.es	
Version 2	2023-09-18	Liese Gilles /VITO/ liese.gilles@vito.be	Small adaptations after GS partners' review of the questionnaires

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Table of Contents

Technical reference _____	7
Document history _____	8
Table of Contents _____	10
H.01: Question for fieldworker about hair sample collection _____	11
I.00: Questionnaire information _____	11
H.02: Question for participant about hair sample collection _____	11

H.01: Question for fieldworker about hair sample collection

Q159: Has the hair sample been collected?

Yes

No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q159.1: Please indicate the reason for missing submission of the hair sample

No consent

Sampling was spontaneously refused

Other reason

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q159.1.1: Other reason, that being _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q152: What is the length of the hair sampled? (length from the scalp, in cm) _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q158: Were there any peculiarities with the sample or participant's answers?

No

Yes

Refused to provide sample

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q158.1: Which ones? _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

I.00: Questionnaire information

Q093: Id (participant) _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q094: Id (interviewer) _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q095: Date of the interview **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q095.1: Day _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q095.2: Month _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q095.3: Year _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q096: Start time **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q096.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q096.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q097: End time **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q097.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q097.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q098: Interview place / interview platform _____ **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

H.02: Question for participant about hair sample collection

Q153: What is the natural colour of the hair?

Black/dark brown

Brown

Blond/fair

Red/strawberry blond

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q154: What is the natural structure of the hair?

ANNEX 4.5 – HAIR SAMPLING QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

Straight

Wavy

Curly

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q157: When was the hair last washed?

Today

Yesterday

Before yesterday

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q157.1: How many days ago? _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**